

ANALYSIS OF TRANSVERSE PLY CRACKS USING COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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SUMMARY

X-ray computed tomography was used to image, in three-dimensions, carbon fibre-epoxy [90/0]_s laminate samples. Combining the technique with *in situ* loading it has been possible to quantify the crack opening displacement (COD) in transverse ply cracks, enabling the determination of the contributions of both mechanical and residual stresses to COD.

Keywords: Transverse ply crack; Synchrotron X-ray tomography; *In situ* loading; Fracture; 3D imaging.

INTRODUCTION

Several types of damage occur in composite laminates under tensile loading, these include: intralaminar damage, delamination and individual fibre breaks [1]. The damage is dependent on the materials used, layup and sample geometry, but, in general, intralaminar damage is the first to form. Transverse ply cracks have therefore been studied extensively and many models exist (for a comprehensive review see [2]). The experimental verification of such models is usually based on the observation of transverse ply crack density and its influence upon the effective modulus of the sample [3,4]. In this paper we will present the result of a study using synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT) to directly image, in three-dimensions, a [90/0]_s sample under *in situ* tensile loading. This allows for a full assessment of the crack opening displacement throughout the transverse ply crack, which can be used for model validation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Laminates plates with a [90/0]_s layup were produced from Hexcel HexPly M21/T700GC carbon fibre-epoxy prepreg, the ply thickness was 250 μm . Plane sided samples with a 1x1 mm² cross-section were investigated. The samples were extracted from the laminate plate using an abrasive water jet. The samples were bonded to Al tabs to allow loading in uniaxial tension in a screw driven loading rig designed for *in situ* use at beamline ID19 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF). 1500 radiographs (with 100 ms exposure time) were taken at equiangular increments over 180°. The X-ray beam used was monochromatic and highly coherent with an energy of 20 keV.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

A sample was imaged at loads of 650 N, 750 N and 880 N. The field of view was only sufficient to capture one transverse ply crack (TPC) in detail (0.7 μm resolution), but subsequent analysis at lower magnification showed that at 880 N, there were eight TPCs in the gauge length with an average spacing of 1.2 mm (and a standard deviation of 0.09 mm); this was approximately five times the ply width. Crack bridging by fibres was observed in TPCs. However, bridging via toughening particles (similar to that observed in 0° splits in the notched samples [5]) was not common.

Figure 1 Sections of the COD maps for the plane sided sample at (a) 650 N and (b) 880N. To the left side of both images is the 0° ply. The average CODs across the ply at both loads are presented in (c).

The cracks were segmented from the surrounding material. Using this data it was possible to obtain the COD maps; as shown in Fig. 1 for 650 N and 880 N. The greyscale in the maps relates to the COD (the darker the greyscale the greater COD). The left edge of the maps is the interply boundary and the right side is near the sample free surface. The through-thickness behaviour is further highlighted in Fig. 1c, which shows the average COD across the ply at the two loads. At the edge of the sample the COD is approximately 12 μm at 650 N and 16 μm at 880 N. The contribution to the COD from mechanical loading has been compared with models provided in [3] and [4] with both models being seen to underestimate the experimental COD values.

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REFERENCES

1. M.T. Kortschot, P.W.R. Beaumont, *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 39 (1990) 289.
2. J-M. Berthelot, *Appl. Mech. Rev.* 56 (2003) 111.
3. S.L. Ogin, P.A. Smith, P.W.R. Beaumont, *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 22 (1985) 23.
4. R. Joffe, A. Krasnikovs, J. Varna, *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 61 (2001) 637.
5. A.J. Moffat, P. Wright, J-Y. Buffiere, I. Sinclair, S.M. Spearing, *Scripta Mat.* 59 (2008) 1043